

Original Article in Public Health

Healthcare Professionals' Discourses on Early Discharge: A Critical Analysis of Perceptions and Practice

Julie Als WAMSAHL^{1*}, Christine Als THOR^{2*}, Kim JØRGENSEN³

¹Medical Department 2 Holbæk Hospital, Denmark. E-mail: Juawap@lejre.dk ORCID: 0009-0005-7508-2789

²Medical Department 2, Holbæk Hospital, Region Zealand, Denmark. E-mail: Chrpe@regionsjaelland.dk
ORCID: 0009-0000-0027-6478

³Roskilde University, Denmark. E-mail: Kimjo@ruc.dk ORCID: 0000-0001-9362-7600

*Corresponding Authors

Abstract

Introduction: Early discharge enables hospitalized patients to continue their treatment at home, reducing hospital stay and promoting recovery in familiar surroundings. However, healthcare professionals' perspectives and decision-making significantly influence the feasibility and success of early discharge. Understanding these perspectives is essential for improving its implementation and addressing potential challenges.

Objective: This study aimed to explore healthcare professionals' discourses on early discharge and assess their impact on its practical application and acceptance in hospital settings. It also examined whether these discourses align with or challenge dominant societal narratives in healthcare.

Method: A critical discourse analysis was conducted, drawing on Fairclough's three-dimensional model within a social constructivist framework. Data were collected through two focus group interviews with staff from a medical ward (N=10). The analysis focused on how early discharge was discussed, and which discursive patterns shaped professional reasoning and decision-making.

Results: Four distinct discourses were identified, predominantly focusing on the limitations of early discharge. While some benefits—such as reduced pressure on hospital resources and enhanced patient autonomy—were acknowledged, the discourses largely emphasized concerns. These included patient safety, insufficient resources, and difficulties applying early discharge to complex cases. The findings reveal a prevailing ambivalence among professionals, with apprehensions about risks and feasibility outweighing early discharge's perceived advantages.

Conclusion: Although early discharge offers clear advantages, the dominant discourses among healthcare professionals tend to focus on barriers and limitations. This creates a reluctance to fully embrace early discharge practices and integrate them into routine hospital care, which could hinder its broader application.

Keywords: Care transitions; Discourse analysis; Early discharge; Hospital-at-home; Length of stay.

Cite this paper as: Wamsahl JA, Thor CA, Jorgensen K. Healthcare Professionals' Discourses on Early Discharge: A Critical Analysis of Perceptions and Practice. *Adv Med Psychol Public Health*. 2026;3(1):67-80. Doi:10.5281/zenodo.16748831

Received: 10 January 2024; Revised: 15 March 2024; Accepted: 30 December 2024; Published Online: 06 August 2025

INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand on hospital resources has led to growing interest in strategies that reduce the length of hospital stays. One such strategy is early discharge, where patients leave the hospital earlier and continue their treatment at home [1]. This approach not only alleviates pressure on hospital capacity but also supports patient recovery in more familiar surroundings [2]. However, the successful implementation of early discharge depends on how it is understood and applied by healthcare professionals in the hospital setting.

The concept of early discharge introduces new responsibilities and challenges for healthcare professionals, who must adapt their practices and perceptions to this evolving healthcare model [3]. Understanding how these professionals perceive early discharge is essential, as their interpretations shape the practical application of this concept in clinical settings [4]. Moreover, these perceptions are influenced by broader social and political discourses that frame healthcare policies and practices.

Background

Political visions are aligned with the principle of proximity in the healthcare sector. In Denmark, there is a political desire for a restructuring of the healthcare system towards a more coherent and patient-centered approach [5]. Research suggests that proximity-based care models, which aim to deliver healthcare closer to patients' homes, can enhance patient satisfaction and reduce healthcare costs [6]. In various political documents, home care is described as an integral component of a patient-centered healthcare system [7]. Studies from other European countries have shown that the shift towards home-based care not only helps reduce hospital readmission rates but also improves the overall patient experience [8].

The shift towards a proximity-oriented healthcare system entails the optimal utilization of digital innovations, which, among other aspects, should facilitate increased care and treatment in the patient's own home. The development of the healthcare system affects social, cultural, and political structures and influences discourses among health professionals in the Danish healthcare system. Early discharge from hospitals aims to address capacity challenges by freeing up space [9], which, as a side benefit, can reduce workload pressure. Research conducted by Sartini et al. (2022) supports the claim that early discharge programs can significantly reduce hospital congestion, especially in departments facing increased demands [10].

The demographic development

The demographic development will inevitably result in an augmented patient population within Danish hospitals in the forthcoming years [11]. This will lead to an increased healthcare service consumption, placing strains on hospital departments and posing challenges to the capacity of the healthcare system in the future [5]. International studies have highlighted similar trends, particularly in countries facing aging populations, suggesting the need for restructuring healthcare services to accommodate this demographic shift [12]. This necessitates efforts that focus on enhancing patient flow and length of stay, which are crucial for hospitals to operate efficiently and cost-effectively. It will be

essential to reevaluate our current understanding of care and treatment concepts, giving rise to new modes of discourse and cause social change.

Discourses in the healthcare system

Within the Danish healthcare system, discourses evolve and develop in line with the progression of the healthcare sector over time [13]. Research has pointed out that professional hierarchies and the division of responsibilities between hospital and municipal care settings often shape these discourses [14]. Scientific studies indicate the existence of a discourse regarding resource distribution between sectors [13]. For instance, balancing resources between hospitals and municipal care is crucial to ensuring that patients receive consistent, high-quality care at all stages of treatment [15].

A gap in the literature

Existing research in the field indicates that using home treatment produces similar or even better clinical outcomes compared to receiving treatment in a hospital setting [2]. This is consistent with findings from a systematic review by Caplan et al. (2012), which provides strong evidence supporting the safety and effectiveness of home treatment for intravenous therapy [16], [17]. Furthermore, several positive benefits of providing treatment to patients in their own homes have been identified, including enhanced patient autonomy, reduced risk of hospital-acquired infections, and better mental well-being [18], [19]. The majority of patients express a desire to receive treatment at home [18], [20], which highlights a growing preference for home-based care models.

While numerous studies have examined the perspectives of patients and their families, fewer have explored the perspectives of healthcare professionals [21]. Specifically, focusing on healthcare professionals in a hospital setting, no relevant literature has been found that addresses their understandings, experiences, and thoughts regarding the process of discharging patients for home-based treatment. International studies have noted similar gaps in other healthcare systems, where the focus has been predominantly on patient outcomes, often neglecting the critical role of healthcare staff in the discharge process [22], [23]. Therefore, there is a gap in the existing literature that focuses on the understandings and perspectives of healthcare professionals in the hospital sector regarding early discharge.

The concept of early discharge

All hospitals in Region Zealand have the opportunity to discharge relevant patients earlier for home-based treatment [24]. The objective is to free up hospital beds and resources for more acute cases while allowing the stable patient to continue their remaining treatment process at home [9]. Studies in the UK and Australia have demonstrated similar outcomes with early discharge programs, where stable patients could safely continue treatment at home, thereby reducing hospital stay lengths and improving patient satisfaction [25].

The patients must have completed the diagnostic process, and the expected treatment time can be up to a few weeks [9]. They must be stable and have a maximum of three daily supervision needs. Meeting these criteria allows patients to be discharged earlier. The municipalities in Region Zealand have a collective daily capacity of 18-22 patients who can receive hospital treatment in their own homes [9]. The concept involves municipal nurses or nurses from the regions home treatment units administering the intravenous medical treatment post-discharge, and the responsibility for treatment remains with the region [9]. Before discharge, the hospital nurses send a care pathway plan for the municipality, and early discharge is further planned based on the patient's treatment and care needs.

Study aim

This article explores the discourses among healthcare professionals regarding early discharge. By analyzing how language and social interactions shape these discourses, the study seeks to uncover the underlying assumptions and power structures that influence the utilization of early discharge. Through this lens, we aim to reveal how healthcare

professionals' understandings of early discharge contribute to its practice within the hospital system and where these understandings originate in a broader societal context.

By employing critical discourse analysis, this study offers insights into the complex relationship between language, social practice, and institutional structures in healthcare. The findings will not only contribute to a deeper understanding of professional discourses on early discharge but also provide a foundation for improving the implementation of this practice in hospital settings.

METHODS

The study adopts a social constructivist epistemology, as it aligns with the assumption that reality, including the concept of early discharge, is socially constructed through language, interactions, and institutional discourses [26]. By applying social constructivism in a discourse analysis, this study explores how healthcare professionals in a hospital context construct and negotiate the meaning of early discharge.

Social constructivism provides a framework for understanding how discourses shape the ways in which early discharge is perceived, discussed, and operationalized by healthcare professionals. This approach emphasizes that their understanding of early discharge is not neutral or objective but is shaped by the social and institutional contexts in which they work [27]. Through discourse analysis, the study uncovers the implicit assumptions and power structures embedded in the language and practices surrounding early discharge, offering insight into how these constructions influence professional decision-making and behavior [28].

The search for discourses

The study analyzes dominant discourses to understand the structures and norms influencing healthcare professionals' actions regarding early discharge. Discourses are shaped by linguistic patterns in communication, which attribute meaning to specific phenomena [29].

Norman Fairclough's discourse framework was used to examine how language and social practices intersect, showing how dominant discourses shape professional behaviors and decision-making [29].

Focus groups

The study employed focus group interviews to collect empirical data, as this method is particularly well-suited to explore how discourses are co-constructed in a social setting [30]. Focus groups allow participants to engage in dialogue, where shared understandings and differences in opinion can emerge, reflecting the social dynamics that shape professional discourses [31]. By facilitating interaction among healthcare professionals, focus groups capture the collective nature of discourse formation and provide insights into how institutional norms and practices influence their perceptions of early discharge [32]. A total of two focus group interviews were conducted. The focus groups aimed to generate understandings and opinions prevailing within the institutional framework of the hospital ward [31]. They provide a space and opportunity for critical engagement and questioning that contributes to reflection on the healthcare professionals' expressed statements [30].

Selection and recruitment

Participants were selected using an analytical sampling approach, ensuring that key characteristics relevant to the research were represented [33]. To recruit participants, a collaborative partnership was established with a medical ward at a hospital. The ward assisted in disseminating information and identifying suitable candidates for the two focus group interviews. Official invitations were then sent to the selected participants.

Settings and participants

Each focus group consisted of five healthcare professionals, including a diverse mix of doctors, nurses, and healthcare assistants. In total ten participants took part in the two focus groups, comprising three men and seven women with a mean age of 42 years. Participants were intentionally chosen from individuals who were already familiar

with one another to create a comfortable environment that encouraged open and inclusive discussion [34]. The interviews took place in familiar surroundings within the ward, fostering a sense of ease and promoting candid dialogue.

Data collection

Two focus group interviews, each lasting 60 minutes, were conducted and recorded using a secure app to ensure confidentiality [35]. A moderator and an observer were present during the interviews. The moderator introduced the topic and posed open-ended questions to encourage in-depth discussion, while allowing flexibility for follow-up questions to explore emerging themes [31].

To ensure systematic in the critical discourse analysis, the interviews were transcribed by one person, maintaining consistency and reliability in the data [35]. Transcription also plays a key role in the interpretive process, allowing detailed examination of the language used [36].

Ethical considerations

This study adhered to the ethical guidelines for nursing research in Nordic countries, ensuring the protection of participants' rights and well-being [37]. Prior to the interviews, participants were fully informed about the study's purpose, and informed consent was obtained to confirm voluntary participation. Participants were made aware of their right to withdraw at any time without repercussions [38]. Confidentiality was rigorously maintained by anonymizing participant data in the transcription process, and interview recordings, which may contain identifying information, were securely stored in accordance with data protection regulations [39].

Data analysis

Fairclough's three-dimensional model was chosen because it offers a robust framework for linking the micro-level analysis of language to broader social structures and ideologies. This is crucial for our study, as it allows us to explore not only the language healthcare professionals use when discussing early discharge but also how these linguistic choices reflect and reinforce the power relations and ideologies inherent in the healthcare system [27]. By examining how discourse operates at the levels of text, practice, and social context, Fairclough's approach enables us to uncover the often-hidden connections between local interactions and larger political and institutional discourses [27]. This comprehensive, multi-level analysis is essential for understanding how discourses shape both professional behavior and the broader policy environment in which early discharge practices are embedded (40).

Text: Modality, transitivity, and metaphors

In the textual dimension, we examined the empirical data by applying a linguistic analysis focusing on grammar, including modalities and transitivity elements [29,41]. No software was used for the linguistic analysis. The analysis of modality and transitivity elements was conducted manually based on close reading of the transcribed focus group interviews, guided by Fairclough's framework and linguistic literature. This aspect of the analysis is essential because it helps uncover how language choices reflect and shape underlying power relations and ideological positions within the discourse [27].

For instance, the use of specific modalities such as expressions of obligation or possibility reveals the level of authority or certainty with which healthcare professionals communicate about early discharge [41]. This, in turn, provides insight into how dominant discourses influence their decision-making and communication with patients [40].

Transitivity elements, which explore how actions, participants, and processes are represented in the text, are another crucial tool for understanding how responsibility is assigned [42]. By analyzing who performs actions and who receives them, we can see whether healthcare professionals are positioned as active or passive participants in the discharge process. This sheds light on power dynamics, particularly in how responsibility for patient care and recovery is distributed between professionals, reflecting broader societal expectations and policies [29].

Additionally, we examined metaphors and the multifunctionality of language in the focus group discussions. These tools play a significant role in shaping the cognitive framework through which professionals understand and communicate about early discharge [43].

Discursive practice

In the second phase of the analysis, we examined how healthcare professionals' statements and perceptions formed discourses. Through intertextuality, we analyzed how their discourses drew upon other texts and pre-existing discourses, reflecting broader social and professional norms [29]. Interdiscursivity highlighted how multiple discourses overlapped within a single communicative event, shaping their approach to early discharge.

The empirical data were treated as a communicative event, enabling us to analyze how discourses were produced, distributed, and consumed [29]. Production referred to how healthcare professionals constructed their language based on prior discourses, distribution examined how these discourses were shared, and consumption focused on how they were interpreted by others [27,40].

Social practice

The third part of the analysis examines social practices by placing the discourses from the hospital within a broader societal context. Fairclough's three-dimensional model helps connect the discursive practices identified in the hospital ward with larger societal discourses [29]. Through the lens of hegemony and ideology, we explore how these discourses either reflect or resist dominant societal narratives [27].

We compared the hospital discourses with existing discourses from the Healthcare Agreement, a key political document shaping Danish healthcare policy. The discourses from the Healthcare Agreement, which emphasize intersectoral collaboration, were identified through prior research and are presented in the article "Governing Citizens and Health Professionals at a Distance: A Critical Discourse Analysis of Policies of Intersectoral Collaboration in Danish Healthcare" [13]. By juxtaposing the hospital discourses with these established discourses, we aimed to explore how healthcare professionals' practices align with or challenge the broader policy-level narratives.

To deepen our analysis, we applied Habermas' system and lifeworld theory [44,45]. The system represents institutional structures focused on efficiency, while the lifeworld reflects relational aspects of care. This helped clarify how healthcare professionals' discourses might be shaped by system-oriented goals like resource allocation and how they may conflict with lifeworld values [44,45].

By combining Fairclough's and Habermas' frameworks, we critically examined how hospital discourses are embedded in societal structures and their impact on communication, roles, and care.

RESULTS

Through the first and second dimension of the analysis, a total of four discourses were identified (Table 1).

Table 1. Overview of discourses on early discharge.

Discourse	Key Points
Patient Discourse	Early discharge positively impacts patients.
	Complex patients receive better treatment in the hospital.
	Early discharge is primarily suited for self-sufficient, uncomplicated patients.
	Implementing early discharge for complex patients is challenging.

Development Discourse	Criteria for early discharge must be adapted to the ward's patient population.
	Capacity needs to be expanded, especially in municipalities without intravenous home care.
	Early discharge is often not feasible for patients in certain municipalities.
	Municipalities struggle with complex cases, making early discharge difficult.
Utility Discourse	Early discharge aims to relieve the healthcare system and provides long-term benefits.
	It decreases hospital-acquired infections and related complications by reducing hospital stay duration.
	Early discharge promotes quicker recovery by allowing treatment in a familiar environment.
Effectiveness Discourse	Early discharge is part of a politically driven agenda focused on efficiency and societal productivity.
	Early discharge may lead to increased busyness in the ward.
	Early discharge will result in the ward having more care-dependent patients

Patient discourse

Within the ward, there exists a patient discourse, with patients being the central focus realized through two distinct perspectives which are treatment and complexity. Regarding early discharge, a positive attitude towards the concept is expressed due to the reduction of potential complications that may arise during hospitalization [46].

Contrary to the positive understanding, experiences regarding the patient population are also drawn upon, where the patients are repeatedly referred to as "complex", which concerns the healthcare professionals when discharging patients before they have completed their treatment. One of the nurses expressed her concern:

Capabilities in the municipality.

"it's important to ensure that when they are discharged earlier to the municipality, they are actually able to handle it so that patients don't get readmitted."

Nurse 1

Thus, the perspective emerges that complex patients are best treated in the hospital, as the municipality is unable to manage the treatment of complex patients.

Additionally, it becomes challenging to arrange early discharge when dealing with patients requiring complex care. This is evident in the following quote:

Fits the self-sufficient

"... there is no doubt that it is easier if the patients are self-reliant"

Doctor 2

Within the patient discourse, two discursive perceptions emerge. On one hand, healthcare professionals consider early discharge to be generally beneficial for patients. On the other hand, a perspective arises that the process

surrounding early discharge complicates its implementation. This discrepancy is further complicated by the healthcare professionals adopting a perspective that the initiative does not benefit those who would benefit most from it, which are the most complex cases. In the focus group, it is expressed:

Not suited for complexity

"It is not really the ones where we think "they will benefit from coming home.""

Nurse 4

And

".. it only helps the strong patient."

Nurse 3

Thus, a perspective emerges within the patient discourse that early discharge is best suited for self-sufficient uncomplicated patients.

Development discourse

The development discourse is formed based on an understanding that there is a need to adjust the criteria for early discharge to the clientele of the ward, which is addressed as complex in order to adapt the initiative to a broader group of patients and utilize it more effectively.

In the empirical data, the criterion of final diagnosis is particularly highlighted, as the healthcare professionals find this criterion problematic which is evident in this following quote:

For the few

"It's a very narrow group of patients that can be considered. Without a diagnosis, they can't be discharged earlier."

Doctor 2

It can be argued that the criteria for early discharge do not align with the flow of the ward, making it difficult to practice. There is a need to expand the capacity, as healthcare professionals experience patients being rejected due to insufficient capacity in the municipalities. This becomes clear in this statement:

Not worth the attempt

".. when I see they live in certain municipalities, I don't even bother trying to get them discharged earlier."

Doctor 2

The experiences of the healthcare professionals are brought to the forefront, where this experience is portrayed as negative. This negative experience influences the discourse and promotes the desire to increase capacity. At the same time, the negative experience has a detrimental consequence, as early discharge is utilized less due to limited capacity in the municipal sector.

The discourse can be interpreted as reflecting a desire to facilitate earlier patient discharge, but the restrictive criteria and limited municipal capacity pose challenges. This has implications for the actions of healthcare professionals in terms of working towards early discharge. It means that they consciously choose to refrain from utilizing the opportunity based on the discourse. Therefore, the discourse is impacting their decision-making process.

Building upon the positive attitude towards early discharge, the consequences of the criteria and capacity lead to a shift in how the initiative is perceived among healthcare professionals. Early discharge transitions from being regarded positively to being viewed in a negative light.

Utility discourse

The healthcare professionals view early discharge as an initiative established due to a strained healthcare system, intended to serve as a relief. Therefore, they see the establishment of the early discharge practice as a positive measure that will create long-term value in the form of reduced busyness if more patients can be discharged earlier for continued treatment at home. The healthcare professionals do not perceive the benefits of the intervention at present and do not

consider it as an initiative that is meant to make a difference in each individual ward. They have a broader societal perspective on the value of the intervention and why it has been established which is expressed in the following quote:

Relief in a broader perspective

"I can't see how it relieves our nursing staff right here and now, because we just get other patients instead. As soon as we send them away, others just come. I've been thinking more broadly about how it can relieve the healthcare system."

Doctor 1

This can be seen as the production of a utility discourse in a greater perspective, based on the understanding that early discharge is meant to reduce the burden on the healthcare system in relation to the increased number of elderly.

Effectiveness discourse

On the other hand, there is another perspective regarding early discharge, where several healthcare professionals' express concerns about the potential consequences of implementing this concept on the hospital ward. This perspective is reflected in the following quotes:

Higher complexity

"But it also leaves all the complex patients inside the hospital."

Nurse 2

The perspective brought up revolves around the clientele that the healthcare professionals are left with if all the self-sufficient patients are discharged earlier. Consequently, the self-sufficient patients appear as a sort of "haven" to receive new complex patients. Moreover, the early discharge of patients leads to a higher flow in the ward, which results in the healthcare professionals experiencing that what should be a relief instead creates space to accommodate even more patients. This perspective is further elaborated in by a doctor in this quote:

Higher workload

"It's nice when there are some cases where we just need to fix a UTI or something. If they disappear and the beds get filled with complex cases, I won't be able to see 6-7 patients per day. So in that way, I can be concerned about the workload it leaves behind at the hospital."

Doctor2

This perspective leads to increased busyness and is interpreted as a potential risk to patient safety and the work environment if early discharge is implemented as a part of the daily practice.

Shaped through societal discourses

The analysis reveals that healthcare professionals are significantly shaped by societal demands for efficiency, influencing discourses at the hospital level with a focus on workflow optimization and system productivity. These align closely with the hegemonic political narratives outlined in the Healthcare Agreement, which prioritize efficiency and resource management in healthcare.

Using Habermas' theory of system and lifeworld, it becomes evident that the system's focus on efficiency has led to the colonization of the lifeworld. This colonization manifests as a shift from communicative, patient-centered care to instrumental action, where healthcare professionals prioritize system-driven goals over relational aspects of care. Modalities in their language, such as expressions of obligation ("must" or "need to"), reflect this system-oriented priority, while transitivity further emphasizes their role as passive agents constrained by institutional pressures, with patients positioned as recipients rather than active participants.

Communication often lacks mutual understanding and fails to achieve patient consensus, underscoring how system imperatives overshadow the lifeworld's relational dimensions. The result is a growing tension between healthcare professionals' practices and broader societal expectations, as patient care becomes secondary to operational demands.

This analysis shows how dominant societal discourses are reproduced within the hospital, reinforcing the focus on efficiency at the expense of patient-centered care.

DISCUSSION

The key findings of the study will then be interpreted through the lenses of Jürgen Habermas' system and lifeworld perspective [45] and the Danish professor of pedagogy Katrin Hjort's profession theory [47]. This dual approach sheds light on the underlying reasons for healthcare professionals' viewpoints and behaviors, and the broader implications for managing early discharge in the department.

Our findings indicate that healthcare professionals prioritize workflow, efficiency, and resource management over patient-centered care. On one hand, this finding aligns with Katrin Hjort's profession theory, which argues that increasing bureaucratization leads to the de-professionalization of healthcare workers, diminishing their autonomy [47]. Professionals, rather than making patient-centered decisions, frame early discharge in terms of managing ward capacity and resource allocation. This is consistent with existing literature that highlights how organizational efficiency often supersedes individualized care in healthcare reforms [48].

However, it is essential to critically examine whether this prioritization necessarily leads to de-professionalization, or if it can be seen as a pragmatic response to systemic constraints. While Hjort's theory points to a loss of autonomy, some scholars argue that adapting to efficiency-driven reforms can still involve professional agency [49]. Healthcare professionals may develop strategies to balance both patient needs and system demands, which could suggest that the profession is evolving rather than being eroded.

Habermas' theory of system and lifeworld further illuminates these dynamics, revealing how the system's emphasis on efficiency colonizes the lifeworld aspects of care [44]. The language used by healthcare professionals reflects this instrumentalization, with discussions focusing more on meeting system targets than fostering patient-centered communication. Fairclough's critical discourse analysis supports the view that language mirrors broader societal power structures, where system efficiency overrides patient-centered communication [27]. Early discharge is framed less as a patient benefit and more as a tool to manage hospital pressures, underscoring how the system's instrumental logic prevails over communicative action.

Yet, this interpretation warrants a more nuanced view. While Habermas' framework is valuable for critiquing the dominance of system logic, it may overlook how professionals, in their day-to-day practices, still find ways to prioritize patient care within these constraints. Studies on street-level bureaucracy, like Lipsky's, suggest that while professionals operate under system demands, they retain a degree of discretion that allows them to negotiate between system needs and patient care [50]. Therefore, the colonization of the lifeworld might not be as absolute as it appears; professionals may still mediate between the two realms, maintaining some space for ethical, patient-centered care.

Additionally, the development discourse within the study shows a strong focus on adapting early discharge criteria and addressing capacity issues, which mirrors Lipsky's theory of street-level bureaucracy. According to this theory, professionals, constrained by systemic pressures, experience a reduction in their decision-making autonomy [50]. This trend aligns with utilitarian ethics, where the greater good of the system takes precedence over individualized care [51]. Existing research supports the idea that reforms prioritizing efficiency restrict the time available for communicative action, further distancing professionals from their ethical duties to patients [52,53].

However, one could argue that this emphasis on system-driven goals does not necessarily undermine ethical care. Efficiency and patient-centered care might coexist, with professionals leveraging efficiency as a means to ensure timely care for a broader patient population. Thus, while the colonization of care is evident, the binary opposition between system and lifeworld might be too rigid. Some studies suggest that professionals can reframe efficiency itself as a form of care, arguing that effective resource management benefits patients overall by preventing delays in treatment [54].

Finally, this shift in focus has significant communicative consequences. As the system's goals take precedence, the patient increasingly becomes a passive recipient of care, while professionals focus on achieving institutional targets. This colonization of care, as described by Habermas, erodes the lifeworld, where relational and communicative care should ideally occur. Kvæl et al. [55] emphasize how the overemphasis on efficiency diminishes opportunities for meaningful interaction, transforming healthcare into a more transactional process. Yet, the critical question remains: is transactional care always detrimental, or could it be a necessary adaptation to modern healthcare's demands?

While an overemphasis on efficiency can undoubtedly diminish opportunities for meaningful interaction, it does not entirely negate the potential for patient-centered care. Instead, professionals may find ways to integrate efficiency with ethical responsibility, ensuring that patient needs are met while also adhering to system demands. Thus, transactional care, while not ideal in all cases, may represent a pragmatic response to the pressures of modern healthcare, where balancing efficiency and care is an ongoing challenge.

Study limitations

This study marks an initial step in identifying gaps in our understanding of early discharge from the perspective of healthcare professionals. However, it only sheds light on one specific approach to early discharge within a single context. Examining discourses in different settings could have provided a more comprehensive understanding of the various perspectives surrounding early discharge [27].

While focus group interviews were deemed the most appropriate method for data collection, this approach can introduce unintended challenges. Hierarchical dynamics, social norms, group effects, and the potential for conformity or polarization can all shape the discourses and potentially obscure a full understanding of prevailing views [31].

Regarding reliability, the methodology, execution of the focus group interviews, and analysis are thoroughly described. However, this does not guarantee that a similar study in a different institutional context would yield identical results. This is not due to a lack of methodological rigor but because, as researchers operating within a social constructivist framework, we cannot detach ourselves from the study. Our involvement and interpretations inherently shape the analysis, contributing to the co-creation of new insights [26,28].

CONCLUSIONS

This study identifies four key discourses surrounding early discharge: patient, development, utility, and effectiveness discourses. These discourses highlight the tensions between system efficiency and patient-centered care, as healthcare professionals navigate the demands of early discharge implementation. Addressing these discourses through policy changes and professional training could enhance the broader application of early discharge and improve healthcare outcomes.

Within the development and complexity discourses, it is evident that early discharge is perceived as challenging to implement for the ward's patient population, primarily because it is seen as suited for self-sufficient patients. There is also concern that replacing these patients with more complex, care-dependent cases could lead to increased strain on the ward.

In the treatment and utility discourses, early discharge is viewed as a strategy to alleviate the burden on hospitals. If adopted more widely, it has the potential to significantly reduce pressure on the healthcare system in the long term.

Author Contributions : Conceptualization: J.A.W.; methodology: J.A.W.; validation: K.J.; formal analysis, C.A.T.; resources: K.J.; data curation: J.A.W.; writing—original draft preparation: J.A.W.; writing—review and editing, C.A.T. and K.J.; supervision: K.J. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Acknowledgments: None.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The Publisher remains neutral regarding jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations. Additionally, the Publisher is not responsible for the accuracy, completeness, or validity of the content of scientific articles published herein. This statement exempts the Publisher from any responsibility regarding the content of scientific articles, which is solely the responsibility of the authors and peer reviewers.

References

1. The healthcare reform - Make Denmark healthier: Ministry of Health; 2022.
[https://www.ism.dk/Media/637831953766403005/Regeringens%20sundhedsudspil%202022%20\(tilg%C3%A6ngelig%20PDF\).pdf](https://www.ism.dk/Media/637831953766403005/Regeringens%20sundhedsudspil%202022%20(tilg%C3%A6ngelig%20PDF).pdf).
Accessed 21 January 2024.
2. Shepperd S, Iliffe S. Hospital at home versus in-patient hospital care. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2005;(3):CD000356.
doi:10.1002/14651858.CD000356.pub2.
3. Sunvisson H, Habermann B, Weiss S, Benner P. Arguing the Cartesian medical discourse with an understanding of the person's life world, lived body, life story and social identity. *Parkinsonism Relat Disord.* 2012;18. doi:10.1111/j.1466-769X.2009.00413.x.
4. Powell BJ, Waltz TJ, Chinman MJ, Damschroder LJ, Smith JL, Matthieu MM, et al. A refined compilation of implementation strategies: results from the Expert Recommendations for Implementing Change (ERIC) project. *Implementation Sci.* 2015;10(1):21.
Doi:10.1186/s13012-015-0209-1.
5. Region Zealand. Healthcare agreement 2019-2023. 2019. Weblog. <http://publikationer.regionsjaelland.dk/det-naere-sundhedsvaesen/sundhedsaftale2019-23/>. Accessed 12 September 2024.
6. Wodchis W, Dixon A, Anderson G, Goodwin N. Integrating care for older people with complex needs: key insights and lessons from a seven-country cross-case analysis. *Int J Integr Care.* 2015;15:10. doi:10.5334/ijic.2249.
7. Region Zealand. Health close to you, Region Zealand's strategy for a close and connected healthcare system. 2019. Weblog. <http://publikationer.regionsjaelland.dk/det-naere-sundhedsvaesen/sundhed-taet-paa-dig/>. Accessed 1 February 2024.
8. Shepperd S, Iliffe S, Doll HA, Clarke MJ, Kalra L, Wilson AD, et al. Admission avoidance hospital at home. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2016;9:CD007491. doi:10.1002/14651858.CD007491.pub2.
9. Region Zealand's Document Portal. Visiting patients for admission to the eHospitalet. 2022. Region Sjællands Dokumentportal (regionsjaelland.dk).
10. Sartini M, Carbone A, Demartini A, Giribone L, Oliva M, Spagnolo AM, et al. Overcrowding in emergency department: causes, consequences, and solutions-a narrative review. *Healthcare (Basel).* 2022;10(9):1625. doi:10.3390/healthcare10091625.
11. Region Zealand. Region Zealand's health profile 2021. 2022. Report No.: ISBN: 978-87-93639-09-6.
12. Christensen K, Doblhammer G, Rau R, Vaupel JW. Ageing populations: the challenges ahead. *Lancet.* 2009;374(9696).
Doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(09)61460-4.
13. Andersen AB, Frederiksen K, Kolbæk R, Beedholm K. Governing citizens and health professionals at a distance: a critical discourse analysis of policies of intersectoral collaboration in Danish healthcare. *Nurs Inq.* 2017;24(4):e12196. doi:10.1111/nin.12196.
14. Kousgaard MB, Scheele CE, Vrangbæk K. Inter-sectoral collaboration in municipal health centres: a multi-site qualitative study of supporting organizational elements and individual drivers. *Int J Integr Care.* 2019;19(2):4196. doi:10.5334/ijic.4196.
15. Wadmann S, Strandberg-Larsen M, Vrangbæk K. Coordination between primary and secondary healthcare in Denmark and Sweden. *Int J Integr Care.* 2009;9:e02. doi:10.5334/ijic.302.
16. Caplan GA, Sulaiman NS, Mangin DA, Aimonino Ricauda N, Wilson AD, Barclay L. A meta-analysis of "hospital in the home". *Med J Aust.* 2012;197(9):doi:10.5694/mja12.10480.
17. Berrevoets MAH, Oerlemans AJM, Tromp M, Kullberg BJ, ten Oever J, Schouten JA, et al. Quality of outpatient parenteral antimicrobial therapy (OPAT) care from the patient's perspective: a qualitative study. *BMJ Open.* 2018;8(11):e024564.
doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2018-024564.

18. Løvschall C, Risør BW, Tayyari Dehbarz N, Jensen LG, Lou S, Carstensen K, et al. Outpatient Parenteral Antibiotic Therapy – A Health Technology Assessment. DEFACTUM; 2021. Report no: ISBN-nr. 978-87-93639-09-6: 978-87-93657-17-5.
19. Ong BS, Ngian VJJ, Yeong C, Keighley C. Out of hospital and in hospital management of cellulitis requiring intravenous therapy. *Int J Gen Med.* 2019;12. doi:10.2147/IJGM.S230054.
20. Wermuth AK, Rasmussen L. Evaluation of citizens' perceived quality of IV treatment in the local area. DEFACTUM. Weblog. Publikationer - DEFACTUM - Social, sundhed og arbejdsmarked; 2022.
21. Leong MQ, Lim CW, Lai YF. Comparison of hospital-at-home models: a systematic review of reviews. *BMJ Open.* 2021;11(1):e043285. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2020-043285.
22. Gonçalves-Bradley DC, Iltis S, Doll HA, Broad J, Gladman JR, Langhorne P, et al. Early discharge hospital at home. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2017;6(6):CD000356. doi:10.1002/14651858.CD000356.pub4.
23. O'Connor E, Dolan E, Horgan F, Galvin R, Robinson K. A qualitative evidence synthesis exploring people after stroke, family members, carers and healthcare professionals' experiences of early supported discharge (ESD) after stroke. *PLoS One.* 2023;18(2):e0281583. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0281583.
24. Region Zealand. eHospitalet - Hospitalized in or close to one's own home, For healthcare professionals. 2023. Weblog. <https://www.e-hospitalet.dk/fagperson/ebehandling-og-forloeb/indlagt-i-ehospitalet>. Accessed 10 September 2024.
25. Williams S, Morrissey AM, Steed F, Leahy A, Shanahan E, Peters C, et al. Early supported discharge for older adults admitted to hospital with medical complaints: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC Geriatr.* 2022;22(1):100. doi:10.1186/s12877-022-02967-y.
26. Berger PL, Luckmann T. *The social construction of reality: a treatise in the sociology of knowledge.* Harmondsworth, Middlesex: Penguin Books; 1991, p. 19-46.
27. Fairclough N. *Critical Discourse Analysis: The Critical Study of Language.* 2nd ed. Oxford: Routledge; 2010.
28. Burr V. *Social Constructionism.* 3rd ed. Oxford: Routledge; 2015. p. 43-64
29. Fairclough N. *Discourse and social change.* Cambridge: Polity Press; 2008.
30. Kitzinger J. The methodology of focus groups: the importance of interaction between research participants. *Sociol Health Illn.* 1994;16(1):103–121. doi:10.1111/1467-9566.ep11347023.
31. Halkier B. Focus groups. *Frederiksberg: Community Literature; 2014, p. 9-51*
32. Wilkinson S. Focus groups in health research: exploring the meanings of health and illness. *J Health Psychol.* 1998;3(3):329–348. doi:10.1177/135910539800300304.
33. Launsø L, Rieper O, Olsen L. *Research about and with people: research types and research methods in social research.* Copenhagen: New Nordic Publishing House; 2011, p. 95-125.
34. Kvale S, Brinkmann S. *Interview: Introduction to a Craft.* 2nd ed. Copenhagen: Hans Reitzel; 2009, p. 376.
35. Brinkmann S, Kvale S. *InterViews: Learning the Craft of Qualitative Research Interviewing.* 3rd ed. Los Angeles: Sage Publications; 2015, p. 171-173, 220-225.
36. Lapadat JC, Lindsay AC. Transcription in research and practice: from standardization of technique to interpretive positionings. *Qual Inq.* 1999;5(1):64–86. doi:10.1177/107780049900500104.
37. SNN. Ethical Guidelines for Nursing Research in the Nordic Countries. 2003. Weblog. https://ssn-norden.dk/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/ssns_etiske_retningslinjer_0-003.pdf. Accessed 9 January 2024.
38. Beauchamp TL, Childress JF. *Principles of Biomedical Ethics.* 6th ed. New York: Oxford University Press; 2009, p. 117-120.
39. General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). European Union. 2016. Art. 32
40. Winther Jørgensen M, Phillips L. *Discourse Analysis as Theory and Method.* Frederiksberg: Community Literature; 2013.
41. Halliday MAK, Matthiessen CMIM. *An Introduction to Functional Grammar.* 3rd ed. London: Arnold; 2004, p. 332-355, 686 - 739
42. Halliday MAK. *An Introduction to Functional Grammar.* London: Edward Arnold; 1998, p.149 – 161.

43. Fairclough N. *Language and Power*. Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge; 2015.
44. Habermas J, Thomas M. *The Theory of Communicative Action*. Boston: Beacon Press; 1984, p. 332-341, 355-373.
45. Nørager T. *System and Lifeworld: Jürgen Habermas's Construction of the Modern*. Frederiksberg: Anis; 1985, p. 45-68.
46. Apollo P. Health and the social individual: analysis of two efficiency concepts. *Forum Sports*. 2010;26(2). doi:10.7146/ffi.v26i2.31607.
47. Hjort K. *Det Affektive Arbejde*. 1st ed. Frederiksberg: Samfundslitteratur; 2012, p. 35- 87.
48. Glette MK, Wiig S. The role of organizational factors in how efficiency-thoroughness trade-offs potentially affect clinical quality dimensions – a review of the literature. *Int J Health Gov*. 2021;26(3):250-265.
49. Noordegraaf M. Reconfiguring professional work: changing forms of professionalism in public services. *Adm Soc*. 2013;45(7):783–810. doi:10.1177/0095399713509242.
50. Lipsky M. *Street Level Bureaucracy: Dilemmas of the Individual in Public Services*. Russell Sage Foundation; 1980, p. 18-34.
51. Ethics Unwrapped. (n.d.). *Utilitarianism*. University of Texas at Austin. Weblog. <https://ethicsunwrapped.utexas.edu/glossary/utilitarianism>. Accessed 5 October 2024.
52. Evetts J. The sociological analysis of professionalism: occupational change in the modern world. *Int Sociol*. 2003;18(2):395–415. doi:10.1177/0268580903018002005.
53. Buzzone C, Petralito M, Fanari F, Villa A. Evaluating patient perceptions of discharge information in a Milan hospital: An observational descriptive study. *Adv Med Psychol Public Health*. 2024;1(4):212-224. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11075479.
54. Martin S, Smith PC. Rationing by waiting lists: an empirical investigation. *J Public Econ*. 2003;85(1):125–144. doi:10.1016/S0047-2727(01)00130-7.
55. Kvæl LAH, Hellesø R, Bergland A, Debesay J. Balancing standardisation and individualisation in transitional care pathways: A meta-ethnography of the perspectives of older patients, informal caregivers and healthcare professionals. *BMC Health Serv Res*. 2022;22(1):430.

Copyright: © 2026 by the authors. Submitted for possible open-access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).